

Randiflorin, a New Pentacyclic Triterpene Lactone and Randilongin, a New *p*-Coumaric Acid Ester from *Randia longiflora* Lamk. Molecular Conformation of Randiflorin†

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Randiflorin (1) and randilongin (5), isolated from the leaves and twigs of *Randia longiflora* (Rubiaceae) together with the main constituent ursolic acid have been shown to be 3 β -acetoxytaraxastan-28,20 β -olide (1) and *n*-dotriacontyl *p*-coumarate (5) respectively, on the basis of spectroscopic and chemical evidence. The stereochemistry based on biogenetic ground and the molecular conformation of randiflorin (1) have been discussed.

RANDIA longiflora Lamk.² (family Rubiaceae) is a large shrub occurring in Assam, Sylhet and Khasia Hills, Chittagong and southwards to Malacca and Penang, Andaman and Nicobar islands and Malaysia. Its berries are used³ in Indo-China as medicine. Earlier work on a few *Randia* species resulted in the isolation of oleanolic acid, leucoanthocyanidin and D-mannitol from *R. uliginosa*⁴, randilic acid A (\equiv 19 α -hydroxyursolic acid) and randilic acid B (\equiv 19-dehydroxyursolic acid) from *R. dumetorium*⁵, and oleanolic acid from *R. brandissii*⁶. Chemical investigation on *R. longiflora* was not reported earlier.

The present paper describes the isolation from the leaves and twigs, and structure elucidation of two minor constituents—a new pentacyclic triterpene

lactone, randiflorin (1) and a new *p*-coumaric acid ester, randilongin (5) along with the isolation of the widely-occurring triterpene, ursolic acid as the main constituent.

The petrol (b.p. 60–80°) extract of the plant material upon chromatography over silica gel yielded from the petrol–benzene (1:1) eluate fractions randiflorin (1; 0.0021%), crystallising from petrol–chloroform mixture as fine needles, m.p. 303–05°, $[\alpha]_D + 34.5^\circ$, C₅₈H₈₀O₄ (M⁺, *m/z* 498), ν_{max} (KBr) 1742 (six-membered lactone), 1728 and 1233 (alcoholic acetate), 1440, 1380 cm⁻¹ (CMe₂). The molecular formula and the positive Liebermann-Burchardt test indicated it to be a triterpene. The ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃; 300 MHz) displayed the presence of six tertiary methyl groups on saturated carbons (3H singlets at δ 0.824, 0.835, 0.840 and 0.893 attributable to the axial methyls at C-4, C-8, C-10 and C-14 respectively and the 3H singlets at δ 0.92 and 1.30 assignable to the equatorial methyls at C-4 and C-20 respectively), one secondary methyl at δ 0.98 (3H, d, *J* 7 Hz), one acetoxy methine proton at the customary C-3 position around δ 4.46 appearing as a double doublet (*J*_{ax} \approx 10 Hz, *J*_{eq} \approx 6 Hz), indicating the axial α -orientation of H-3 and an acetate methyl at δ 2.04 (3H, s). The acetoxy group at C-3 was thus indicated to be β - and equatorial. The downfield signal (δ 1.30) is attributable to the α -methyl at C-20 which is linked through the δ -lactonic oxygen to the C-28 forming the lactonic CO on the β -face. The above spectral characteristics together with the absence of any vinylic proton, negative colouration with TNM and the molecular composition suggested it to be a saturated pentacyclic triterpene acetate with a lactone ring.

The mass fragmentation pattern (Scheme 1) of randiflorin was fully consistent with its assigned structure 1 having taraxastane skeleton⁷ with a six-membered δ -lactone in ring E linking C-28 and

† Part-28 of the series 'Terpenoids and Related Compounds'; For Part-27 see Ref. 1. The major part of this work was reported in Part-IV of the Ph.D. Thesis of A. C. Sarkar, Calcutta University, 1980.

Scheme 1. Mass fragmentation of randiflorin (1).

C-20 from β -face. The diagnostically significant peaks retaining rings A and B were fragment ions (a), (a'), (c), (e) and (h), whereas those retaining rings D and E were fragment ions (b), (b'), (d), (f),

(f'), (i), (j) and (k). The fragment ions arose by (i) RDA type collapse of, or 8-14 bond fission with simultaneous 1,4 H-migration in the sterically compressed ring C, or (ii) by loss of CO, CO₂,

(with concomitant 1,2 H-migration in ring E). Me or H from the appropriate ions, or (iii) by RDA collapse of the cyclohexene ring of appropriate ions.

Randiflorin (1) upon saponification produced the corresponding deacetylrandiflorin (2), crystallising from chloroform-ether mixture as needles, m.p. 284–86°. $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 17.5$, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$ (M^+ , m/z 456), ν_{max} (KBr) 3440 (OH) and 1730 cm^{-1} (δ -lactone). The 1H nmr spectrum (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) confirmed the presence of five tertiary methyl groups on saturated carbons (3H singlets at δ 0.77, 0.83, 0.90, 0.93 and 0.96), the tertiary methyl at C-20 carrying the δ -lactonic oxygen (the deshielded 3H singlet at δ 1.30) and an equatorial secondary methyl group at C-19 (3H doublet at δ 0.98, $J \approx 7$ Hz). The singlets at δ 0.77, 0.83, 0.90 and 0.93 are attributable to the axial methyls at C-4, C-10, C-8 and C-14 respectively, and the singlet at δ 0.96 is therefore assigned to the C-4 equatorial methyl group. The secondary alcoholic methine proton at C-3 is now shifted upfield by 1.28 ppm appearing as a doublet at δ 3.18 ($J_{aa} \approx 10$ Hz and $J_{ab} \approx 6$ Hz), expected for equatorial and β -orientation of the 3-hydroxyl group.

The stereochemistry of all the chiral centres has been tentatively suggested as in 1 based on biogenetic grounds. In all probability, taraxasteryl acetate (3) would be the biogenetic precursor of randiflorin (1). Thus 3, in presence of suitable enzymes in plant cells, may undergo biogenetic oxidation at C-28 to produce the corresponding carboxylic acid which should spontaneously attack the 20-30 double bond at C-20 from the axial β -face (satisfying the stereoelectronic requirement) in its boat-like conformation (3a') of the flexible ring E (3a) to form the δ -lactone ring linking C-28 with C-20 and thus would formally produce 1. On the other hand, the 28-oic acid produced from ψ -taraxasteryl acetate (4) is expected to attack at C-21 of ring E in the half-chair form (4a) in a similar fashion from the axial β -face with concomitant protonation at C-20 from the axial α -face to produce the γ -lactone ring between C-28 and C-21 in 4a'. However, in absence of any biosynthetic evidence the above biogenetic pathway is just a speculative possibility. Direct chemical correlation of 1 and 3 which could not be achieved as yet due to paucity of 1, is planned to be undertaken in future.

All the foregoing evidence led to the structure of randiflorin as 3 β -acetoxytaraxastan-28, 20 β -olide (1). Inspection of Dreiding model of 1 revealed that ring E bearing the δ -lactone ring at the 1,4-positions as well as the δ -lactone ring itself must assume, as expected, rigid boat conformation like the bicyclo[2,2,2]octane system. Randiflorin, therefore, possesses the unequivocal chair-chair-chair-chair-boat-boat conformation (1a) for its all-*trans*-A-B-C-D-E and the δ -lactone rings.

The chloroform extract of the defatted plant material on chromatography over silica gel afforded

from the petrol-benzene (1 : 1) eluate fractions another new natural product, randilongin (5), crystallising from chloroform-petrol as a microcrystalline solid (0.003%), m.p. 82°, $C_{41}H_{72}O_8$ (M^+ 612); ν_{max} (KBr) 3400 (phenolic OH), 1710 (ester CO), 1682 (conjugated ester C=O), 1170 (ester O-CO), 980 (*trans* CH=CH), 830 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene), 730 and 719 cm^{-1} (methylene chain⁸).

The 1H nmr spectrum ($CDCl_3$; 80 MHz) of 5 confirmed the presence of a *p*-disubstituted-benzene ring (δ 7.55, d, H-2 and H-6, J_{ortho} 8.7 Hz, 6.78, d, H-3 and H-5, J_{ortho} 8.7 Hz), a *trans*-disubstituted double bond (7.57, 1H, d, H_A, and 6.23, 1H, d, H_B, J_{AB} 16 Hz), α -CH₂ of the fatty alcohol chain coupling with β -CH₂ (4.15, t, J 6.8 Hz), terminal CH₂ coupling with adjacent CH₂ (0.99, t, J 6 Hz); the rest 60 protons of the fatty alcohol chain appeared in the region δ 1.22–1.75. The mass spectrum showed M^+ peak at m/z 612 and other important peaks at m/z 164 and 147 (derived from the *p*-hydroxycinnamoyl moiety) and at m/z 41 and 41+14n, where n=1 to 8, the relative intensities of the latter

peaks decreasing with increasing mass—a characteristic of straight chain fatty alcohols⁹, peaks upto $n=8$ being discernible (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Mass fragmentation of randilongin (5).

Randilongin (5) was hydrolysed (5% KOH-MeOH) and the product after usual work-up was methylated (CH_3N_2) without further purification. The resulting mixture (two spots) upon chromatography over silica gel yielded a low melting fatty compound, characterised as *n*-dotriacontanol, $C_{32}H_{66}O$ (M^+ 466) from its physical constants, and methyl *p*-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamate, $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ (M^+ 192), identified through its physical properties and direct comparison.

The major component of the petrol as well as $CHCl_3$ extractives was eluted from the main chromatograms by $CHCl_3$ -MeOH (95 : 5) mixture and was identified as the triterpene ursolic acid, crystallising from ethanol as colourless needles (0.28%), m.p. 290°, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$ (M^+ 456).

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillaries using a Toshniwal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Petrol refers to light petroleum (b.p. 60–80°). The ir spectra (KBr) were run on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer, 1H nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a 300 MHz Varian EM 390 or Jeol 100 MHz spectrometer, the δ -values (ppm) being downfield from TMS, and mass spectra measured at 70 eV using a direct inlet system. The silica gel (B.D.H., 60–120 mesh) and silica gel G (B.D.H.) were used for cc and tlc respectively and the spots were visualised on exposure to iodine

vapour. The plant material was collected from the garden of the Royal Agri-Horticultural Society of India, Calcutta during July 1978 when in full leaf.

Extraction : Air-dried and powdered leaves and twigs (2 kg) were exhaustively extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with petrol and $CHCl_3$ in succession for 40 h each. The residues A (≈ 22 g from petrol extract) and B (≈ 18 g from $CHCl_3$ extract) obtained upon evaporation under reduced pressure were found to be devoid of any alkaloidal constituent (negative Dragendorff test).

Isolation of randiflorin (1) : The residue A was chromatographed over silica gel (main chromatogram), elution being carried out with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity. The residue from petrol-benzene (1 : 1) eluate fractions was rechromatographed on silica gel. The fractions eluted with the same solvent mixture afforded pure randiflorin (1), crystallising from $CHCl_3$ -petrol mixture as light grey needles (42 mg), m.p. 303–05° (Found : C, 76.82; H, 10.20. $C_{30}H_{48}O_4$ requires : C, 77.10; H, 10.04%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} +34.5^\circ$ (c 0.1, $CHCl_3$); ν_{max} (KBr) 2980 (CH and CH_2), 1742 (δ -lactone), 1728 and 1233 (alcoholic acetate), 1440, 1380 (CMe_2), 1370, 1355, 1200, 1077, 1020, 989 and 945 cm^{-1} ; EI MS m/z (rel. int.) 498 (M^+ , 6) 438 (M^+ -AcOH, 54), 423 (438-Me, 21), 395 (*g* or *g'*, 100), 249 (*a* or *b*, 7), 234 (*d*, 14), 233 (*i*, 14), 220 (*j*, 7), 205 (*b''*, 14), 204 (*c*, 14), 203 (*h*, 18), 192 (7), 189 (*a'*, 46), 177 (*f'*, 18.8), 176 (*k*, 22), 175 (*e*, 22), 109 (*l*, 38), 107 (*m*, 57), 81 (*n* or *o*, 47) and 69 (*p*, 62).

Hydrolysis of randiflorin (1) to form deacetyl-randiflorin (2) : Randiflorin (1; 5 mg) was refluxed on a water-bath with 5% methanolic KOH (10 ml) for 6 h. The reaction mixture, after dilution with water (10 ml), was concentrated under reduced pressure to drive away MeOH, cooled and extracted with ether (3 × 25 ml). The solid residue obtained after removal of ether from the dried ether extract was crystallised from $CHCl_3$ -petrol to afford deacetylrandiflorin (3 mg) as needles, m.p. 284–86°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +17.5^\circ$, $C_{28}H_{44}O_3$ (M^+ , m/z 456); ν_{max} (KBr) 3440 (OH), 2925 (CH and CH_2), 1735 (δ -lactone), 1450, 1385 (CMe_2), 1230 (O-CO), 1100, 1070, 1050, 955 and 755 cm^{-1} .

Isolation of ursolic acid : The $CHCl_3$ -MeOH (95 : 5) eluate fractions of the main chromatogram furnished ursolic acid, crystallising from absolute ethanol as colourless needles (4 g, 0.2%), m.p. 290°, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$ (M^+ 456), $[\alpha]_D^{25} +85^\circ$ (EtOH, c 0.14); the acetate, m.p. 275°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +67^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.02). The identities of both the compounds were confirmed by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic samples¹⁰.

Isolation of randilongin (5) : The petrol-benzene (1 : 1) eluate fractions of the main chromatogram of the $CHCl_3$ extract B afforded a solid, showing a spot on tlc (R_f , 0.8; $CHCl_3$ -MeOH, 98 : 2), which upon chromatography over silica gel (100–200 mesh) yielded from the benzene eluate fractions pure randilongin, crystallising from $CHCl_3$ -petrol

as microcrystalline solid (60 mg), m.p. 82°; EIMS (Scheme 2) m/z (rel. int.) 612 (M^+ , 61), 448 (1.5), 164 (100), 153 (=41+14×8) (2), 139 (=41+14×7) (1.3), 120 (31), 125 (=41+14×6) (3.3), 111 (=41+14×5) (7), 97 (=41+14×4) (14), 83 (=41+14×3) (17), 69 (=41+14×2) (22), 55 (=41+14) (24) and 41 (12).

The CHCl_3 -MeOH (95:5) eluate fractions afforded upon rechromatography a further amount of crystalline ursolic acid (1.5 g).

Hydrolysis of randilongin (5). Isolation of *n*-dotriacontanol and *p*-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamic acid as its methyl ester: Randilongin (5; 30 mg) was refluxed with 5% KOH-MeOH (20 ml) on a steam-bath for 1 h. The reaction mixture, after neutralisation with dilute HCl and evaporation of MeOH, was extracted with CHCl_3 . The CHCl_3 extract was washed, dried and evaporated. The residue obtained was dissolved in MeOH and treated with an ethereal solution (excess) of CH_3N_2 in ice-cold condition. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure, and a CHCl_3 solution of the residue showing two spots on tlc (R_f , 0.3 and 0.7; silica gel G, benzene) was chromatographed over silica gel (100–200 mesh). The petrol-benzene (1:1) eluate fractions afforded *n*-dotriacontanol, crystallising from petrol- CHCl_3 mixture as microcrystalline solid (8 mg), m.p. 88–9°, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{66}\text{O}$ (M^+ 466); ν_{max} (KBr) 3400 (OH), 2960, 2940 (CH_2 and CH_3), 730 and 720 cm^{-1} . The benzene- CHCl_3 (1:1) eluate fractions of the above chromatogram afforded methyl *p*-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamate, crystallising from CHCl_3 -petrol mixture as colourless flakes (9 mg), m.p. 90°, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ (M^+ 192); ν_{max} (KBr) 1705 (ester CO), 1620 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$

conjugated with *p*-methoxyphenyl), 1595, 1580, 1150, 970 (*trans*- $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$), 825 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene) and 710 cm^{-1} .

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of a Teacher Fellowship (to A.C.S.) and a Junior Research Fellowship (to S.C.), to G.B. Panskura Banamali College, Midnapur, W. Bengal for the grant of leave (to A.C.S.), to the University of Calcutta for financial assistance, and to Dr. D. Mukherjee, Secretary, Royal Agri-Horticultural Society of India, Calcutta, for identification and supply of the plant material.

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